

Nanoaerobic Vertical Bioreactor System (NVBS®) Risk Assessment: Wastewater Treatment Technology as a Resilient Solution After Climate-Related Events

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The new global reality regarding climate events is a reality that cannot be denied and that will occur with extreme frequency over the years. Robust and comprehensive wastewater treatment systems are not adequate to deal with these events, and are always impacted by secondary damage that causes serious public health problems and has a high cost of repair. The Vertical Nanoaerobic Bioreactor System (NVBS®) is suitable to withstand these events and should be evaluated as a model of resilient and rapidly recovering healthcare management.

Summary:

Secondary damage after climate-related events is about three times more costly than the immediate effects of devastation. Public health diseases and epidemiological conditions, such as environmental impacts caused by pollution, are dangerous effects on the availability of safe drinking water and sanitation control. Water utilities and public infrastructure must enhance existing safety and preparedness efforts with innovative and outstanding solutions to meet unprecedented challenges. This article evaluated the wastewater treatment technology, Nanoaerobic Vertical Bioreactor System (NVBS®) designed for a Panamanian Caribbean island, as a resilient solution after climate-related events in a risk matrix of water components. Climate-related events and impacts on management and operation, infrastructure damage, infrastructure recovery, public health impacts were evaluated.

Keywords:

Climate Related Events, Risk Matrix, Water, Wastewater, Sanitation Control, Public Health, Water Services, Nanoaerobic Vertical Bioreactor System (NVBS®), WWT Technology

1. Introduction

Weather-related hazards and disaster-related deaths are overwhelmingly caused by the initial traumatic impact of a major event. However, the long-term health effects associated with epidemic diseases after natural disasters, large or small, are underestimated and, in the long term, it is one of the major public health problems in the affected region. It is often the result of inadequate access to clean water and sanitation facilities, because both are damaged after an event.

The Florida Water/Wastewater Agency Response Network indicates that secondary damage after weather-related events is approximately three times more costly than the immediate effects of devastation (FlaWARN, 2019)

The key issue with water management in the future is not only that climate change predictions are uncertain, but also that the climate will be unstable and unpredictable based on long-term historical data. (Costello A., 2009)

The history of climate-related hazards and disasters shows that the risk of diarrheal disease outbreaks after natural disasters was reported in 85% of residents in the city of Calang, Indonesia, 2 weeks after the December 2004 tsunami. In addition, hepatitis A and hepatitis E clusters were observed.

In Taiwan, Republic of China, there were outbreaks of leptospirosis associated with Typhoon Nali in 2001; in Mumbai, India, after the 2000 floods; and in other places affected by climate-related disasters. Outbreaks of malaria and dengue fever following floods are a well-known phenomenon. More complex diseases, such as tetanus and rabies, are also reported.

The long-term health effects associated with epidemic diseases after natural disasters are related to the availability of safe drinking water and sanitation. The priority of water after an event focuses on drinking water. Wastewater is the latest action taken, but it is the one that is having a major impact on public health and the environment. Sanitation must be a priority in the affected areas, creating a real capacity to absorb impacts through protective risk reduction technology.

All wastewater systems have value as a key driver of risk management in climate hazards. They should have other characteristics related to other principles, such as continuous improvement and stakeholder inclusion, personalization of the organization, and consideration of human and cultural factors.

The Nanoaerobic Vertical Bioreactor System (NVBS) is a unique technology from WWT that can reduce the risk of epidemic diseases after climate-induced natural disasters because it is the only one that keeps operational after that. We can take it on as a sustainable solution.

The NVBS is a solution that, due to its characteristics as part of a systematic sanitation project, would quickly recover and restore treatment efficiency after a major impact or event.

The NVBS consists of a set of interconnected tanks and reactors with wastewater purification and digestion of organic biomass through liquid transport, gas transport and solids control (LAUCEVICIUS, 2014). It uses compressed air as a motive force, through density pumps, and as a promoter of biological reactions.

Why Is Sewer and Wastewater Infrastructure Damaged After Weather-Related Events?

Extreme storms and precipitation, flooding, sea level rise, heat waves, and others, can affect pipeline infrastructure causing breaks or blockages; and impacting wastewater treatment plants (WWT) causing overflow and damage to machinery. These damages have high repair costs and in a disaster scenario, it is a low priority.

Sewer pipes and infrastructure are preferably underground. It is made of sturdy material and any movement to fix it requires a lot of activities. WWT's conventional plants are open tanks equipped with pumps, motors, and equipment that are highly susceptible to damage after misuse.

As a Sanitation Policy for WWT's topic after climate disaster, it should include several steps: quickly restore wastewater service after an emergency, minimize damage to the wastewater system; minimize negative impacts on public health and safety, minimize adverse effects on the environment, provide wastewater system information for first responders and other outside agencies.

The NVBS designed for two islands in the southern Panamanian Caribbean region, which are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change and therefore vulnerable to such disasters, could be a sustainable sanitation system that is economically viable, socially acceptable, and technically and institutionally appropriate, as well as protects the environment and natural resources.

These islands were hit on November 23, 2016 by Hurricane Otto, the last hurricane of the season, and the southernmost to occur in the last century, as a result of the processes generated by Climate Change.

Although, at this time, we witnessed how the force of Hurricane Otto affected the structures of the former wastewater treatment plant, located on the coast of the island. Tank overflow and flooding of the adjoining slum were observed. The old wastewater treatment plant lost full operation and could never be reactivated, forcing the design and construction of a new wastewater treatment plant.

1. Materials and Methods

The NANOAEROBIC VERTICAL BIOREACTOR SYSTEM (NVBS) was designed for the island, with an estimated population of 18,000 inhabitants in 25 years, it is composed of four decentralized parts, in different parts of the island, which congregate at a single point. This reduces the chance of all modules going down at the same time. Also, in the event of a total breakdown, module activation reduces costs and allows the health condition not to be totally neglected.

PROCESS FLOW DIAGRAM - NANO AEROBIC VERTICAL BIOREACTOR SYSTEM WWT

Technical Study for "ISLA COLÓN" Sanitation Project. Flow: 12,000 hab.eq + 6,000 hab.eq in growing = Total Capacity: 16,000 hab.eq

In addition, NVBS does not produce sludge, eliminating the potential effects of sludge accumulation at waste disposal sites. Accumulated sludge is a source of health problems, especially during natural disasters, as it can be "washed" to the population. This model can be replicated throughout the region that is vulnerable to natural disasters.

NVBS are health and hygiene, eliminating the risk of exposure to pathogens and hazardous substances in the watershed because it is entirely underground, reducing the dispersion of pollutants to surrounding communities. Maintenance requires minimal contact with wastewater. In the event of flooding, the system has a reduced inflow of water outside the process, and its construction technique works like a boat, keeping its structure intact.

NVBS protect the environment and natural resources, including inputs and emissions in the system, does not generate sludge and has a greenhouse gas emission percentage 75% lower than the emissions baseline. The treated water is compatible with discharge into natural water bodies while respecting the environment.

The technology and operation, including construction, operation, and monitoring, are robust because the NVBS is automated, requiring minimal need for operation, which can occur remotely. It has no mechanical parts in contact with wastewater, which increases the lifespan of all your equipment. Repairs are doable to find at any local store.

For financial and economic issues, including the ability to pay for sanitation and its costs and benefits and potential externalities, NVBS maintenance costs are compatible with developing countries, estimated at US\$1 per person, making it possible to finance local government facilities.

The use of the NVBS goes hand in hand with a commitment to strong environmental education, generating a sense of belonging for the populations served. Women are an important part of the system, from scientific, managerial and executive positions.

The NVBS operates within a closed circuit consisting of four independent, interconnected, non-recirculating tanks. It is classified as Combined Biological Wastewater Treatment where an Aerobic Element is observed under the process of activated sludge of Deep Well, aerobic fluidized bed reactor, aerobic digestion process, secondary sedimentation reactor; Another anoxic element with suspended growth process and finally an anaerobic element, through an anaerobic biological filtration process.

With this configuration, according to a study presented at congresses, NVBS achieves a BOD5 removal efficiency of more than 95% and manages another term called "Bioeffectiveness of Organic Matter Removal", which consists of evaluating the overall efficiency of the system, including the production of sludge, handling a value of 90% Bioeffectiveness. The higher the bioeffectiveness, the lower the sludge production.

All NVBS is fully underground and protected from flooding. The parts in contact with wastewater are made of plastic and materials that are easy to buy in local markets. The most complex piece of equipment is the air compressor system, which is easily replaceable. When the NVBS stops working, it maintains the aerobic treatment of the wastewater for up to 3 days and after this period, it activates an anaerobic treatment that has a BOD removal efficiency of 40%.

That is, in the event that the air compressor system is damaged by the effects of natural disasters, the system keeps the treatment at a lower efficiency, never leaving the user totally unattended.

Due to its compact and modular design, the treatment parts eliminate pumping stations, allowing the sewer system to be smaller gauge and therefore easy to replace.

1. Results and Discussion

For this article we use international quality management parameters, based on the guidelines of the ISO 31000 Risk Management standard. It is important to note that ISO 31000 provides guidelines, not requirements, and is therefore not intended for certification purposes.

(Fuente: ISO 31000:2009(E))

We created the Risk Framework using the measurement tool created in accordance with the UN's Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), where climate risk can be qualitatively defined as "The probability over a specific period of time of severe disruptions to the normal functioning of a community or society due to physical hazards, events that interact with vulnerable social conditions, leading to adverse human, pervasive material, economic, or environmental effects"

INTEGRATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralization or Decentralization?
STRUCTURE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Architectonic protection • Operation challenges
VERSATILITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One size for all??
INCLUSION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need of Human Resource • Decision Makers
DYNAMIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variability of existing reactions • Bottleneck
INFORMATION DISPONIBLE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Quality • Tests and Analisis
SOCIO-POLITIC FACTO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for investment • Priorization Level • Implementation route
UPGRADES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control • Redesign and Calibration

The installed NVBS® TECHNOLOGY is a decentralized system in three modules located by sanitation clusters that can act independently in case of a requirement for damage to any part or piece of the system. Thus, the total treatment of the island will never be completely affected, unless there is total devastation of the area.

The structure of the wastewater treatment plant is mostly located underground in hermetically sealed tanks, not being affected in the event of hurricanes, floods, tsunamis, fires or weather events that may affect the island. The structure located on the surface consists of the control booths containing the electromechanical equipment. These are simple infrastructures that do not require complex works, being easy to repair. The equipment located in them is also easily found in specialized markets (compressors, blowers, hoses and pressure gauges, electrical structure) allowing for easy replacement if required. The VERTICAL NANOAEROBIC BIOREACTOR SYSTEM (NVBS) does not require many personnel in the plant, due to its simplicity and robustness, allowing few people to be involved in case of requirements generated by climatic events.

The design of the NVBS® TECHNOLOGY is specific for each area of implementation, being carried out based on geological, population, economic, and environmental characteristics according to a specific and meticulous study of the area of application.

The model designed for the island is self-managed and automated, allowing decision-making and staff use to be minimized during critical periods following the weather event.

Due to its versatility, NVBS® TECHNOLOGY has various types of biological, physical and chemical reactions that, in the worst scenario, the efficiency of wastewater treatment is never less than 40% since it is capable of working in an anaerobic biological way until the restoration of electric power services. This feature also makes the system recover quickly when the operational requirements are met, having an immediate boot-up.

The system can be visually evaluated during initial recovery, without the need for costly testing and analysis, with simple observation of wastewater color, hydraulic movement in tanks, observation of airflow. This data, obtained in a simple way, is of sufficient quality to evaluate the operability of the system until more complex analyses are carried out.

The investment required for the implementation of the system was competitive with the use of conventional systems, being in a range of 90-150% of the price of the other technologies proposed. In risk assessment, NVBS® TECHNOLOGY has up to 100% lower recovery costs. When a climate event occurs, the level of prioritization of recovery investment may be at the bottom levels as it should not suffer significant impacts.

After the event, the system recovers to operational levels without requiring redesign. Its operational adjustments and calibration are immediate.

1. Conclusions

NVBS® TECHNOLOGY is a resilient solution to extreme weather events and should be exploited as feasible to be installed in areas that have had recurrent damage to healthcare infrastructure due to these events.

The NANOAEROBIC VERTICAL BIOREACTOR SYSTEM allows the response to the event to be focused on paramount human priorities, without omitting assistance to wastewater treatment. This prevents secondary public health and environmental effects due to fecal contamination in impacted areas and reduces tertiary expenses due to post-event problems.

The system has normal operation when there is no event and also has lower routine operation and maintenance costs. During the event, the system is easy to recover.

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